

Bridging tradition and innovation: Enhancing agriculture through social relations and effective communication

Minh-Phuong Thi Duong

Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Ton Duc Thang University, Ho Chi Minh City,
Vietnam

May 20, 2024

~~~

“In reality, convincing the birds is a hefty task. If anything is nonsensical, they will pretend to listen and gossip behind his back, which would only damage his reputation.”

In “The Philosopher Bird”; [The Kingfisher Story Collection](#) [1]

## [WORLDVIEW]

Promoting agricultural technologies and advancements in farming techniques has long been recognized as crucial for improving farmer livelihoods, supporting rural development, and adapting to climate change [2]. However, despite these acknowledged benefits, introducing new agricultural practices and techniques often encounters resistance from farmers who maintain traditional practices [3]. Frequent concerns arise regarding the complexity of equipment, maintenance costs, and doubts about their impact on crop yields.

Simultaneously, village elders, symbolizing the established social hierarchy, regard these technological advancements with skepticism, fearing potential disruptions to the community’s power balance. This skepticism, combined with decades of limited success in increasing adoption rates and reducing poverty, highlights the necessity for reassessing

agricultural extension methods [4].



**Illustration.** Generated by Imagine AI (<https://www.imagine.art/>)

The primary reason for this lack of enduring change is the neglect of social relations within agricultural communities. The conventional provisionist model, focused on delivering technology, information, and capital, overlooks the significant social dynamics that shape farmer behavior [3].

To achieve meaningful and sustainable enhancements in agricultural practices, prioritizing the fostering of supportive social relations is important. This requires adopting an approach centered on social interactions and networks, recognizing that successful adoption relies on resource availability and cultivating conducive community relationships capable of driving long-term transformation [5].

In addition to addressing social dynamics, effective science communication has proved crucial in improving agricultural practices, particularly those related to climate change adaptation. By utilizing various media formats and designing communication strategies for different stakeholders, information becomes more accessible and resonates better with farmers.

Engaging farmers and agricultural experts in sharing their experiences with agricultural practices and climate change impacts can help enhance involvement and understanding

among participants [6]. Moreover, establishing interactive platforms where farmers can explore agricultural practices in the context of climate change adaptation strategies enhances learning effectiveness. This can improve feasibility and foster greater motivation for action among various stakeholders, ultimately contributing to more effective responses to agricultural challenges in the face of climate change [6].

## References

- [1] Vuong QH. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>
- [2] Lybbert TJ, Sumner DA. (2012) Agricultural technologies for climate change in developing countries: Policy options for innovation and technology diffusion. *Food Policy*, **37**(1), 114-123. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0306919211001345>
- [3] Cook BR, *et al.* (2021). Humanising agricultural extension: A review. *World Development*, **140**, 105337. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305750X20304642>
- [4] Barrie H, *et al.* (2010). New technologies: Their potential role in linking rural older people to community. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Society*, **68**. [[URL](#)]
- [5] Wedajo DY, Jilito MF. (2020). Innovating social connectedness for agricultural innovations in eastern Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, **6**(1), 1809943. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23311932.2020.1809943>
- [6] Nguyen MH. (2024). Five principles to leverage the humanistic values for biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. <https://mindsponge.info/posts/307>

